

Item	ONBOARDING: Your responsibility as a new team member	Link	OFFBOARDING: Your responsibility as an alumnus	Notes (to be removed before publishing)
Overlap	If you are replacing someone, please ensure transfer of knowledge has been completed and learn as much as you can from them before they leave.	N/A	If someone is replacing you, speak to them as much as you can before you leave. Make sure they know how to get onboarded.	
Orientation	Review any documents on project summaries, relevant papers, etc.	Provide links to relevant documentation here.		
Governance	Study the Governance document and let your operations or project manager know of any questions. When ready, send a written note to them and the team to let them know you approve and agree with its contents.	Add link to governance document here.	N/A	
Email	Send a request to [email for your operations or manager] for a lab/project email address; this may be needed for access to Google Drive.	N/A	Surrender your Lab address in the agreed upon timeline.	
Calendar	Make sure you have access to the lab/project calendar.	Add link to calendar here.		
Mailing List	Send a request to subscribe to the Lab/Project Mailing List and Google Group using your primary email address (all notifications). If different from the primary one, join also with your Gmail address (no notifications). Should you run into any problems, email the lab admin (add email here) to resolve membership and access.	Include link to subscribe to google group here.	Unsubscribe from ALL google groups that use your lab address. Certain google groups may be joinable again with your personal gmail should you choose to stay in the loop. <i>You can check out any time, but you can never leave... ;)</i>	
Google Suite Documents	The list serve above will drive access to Lab/Project Team Drive	Add link here to Lab/Project team drive.	Unsubscribing from the group will remove access to docs	
Contact info	Add to the lab's/project's roster spreadsheet details about your title, contact info, and area of expertise Let your operations/lab manager know when you've finished so they can add you to GitHub, etc.	Create a spreadsheet of lab member information and share the link here.	Please remove yourself. Please provide your forwarding contact information to your operations or lab manager.	
GitHub	Request membership in your Lab's/Project's GitHub organization. Please set your membership in the Lab/Project Organization to 'Public.' You can either do this when you first confirm that you are joining the organization, or by finding your entry in the list of 'People' that belong to the organization.	Add link for Lab's/Project's GitHub organization.	Email operations or lab manager to request being removed from the GitHub Organization	
Website	Add your details to the lab/project website. Provide instructions here how to do so. Add your image to the lab/project website.	Add link to Lab's/Project's website. Add link to Lab's/Project's website.	Please remove yourself or ask to be removed. Please remove yourself or ask to be removed.	
Slack	Join the relevant work spaces on Slack	Add links to Slack workspaces.	Please leave both the workspaces on Slack.	
Introductions	So we can best introduce you to the team, please consider sharing with your supervisor a picture of yourself and a list with some of your hobbies	N/A	Please provide your forwarding contact information to the operations or lab manager.	